

KASR TARTIBLI DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR UCHUN GALYORKIN USULI

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada biz kasr tartibli differensial tenglamalar uchun boshlangʻich hamda chegaraviy shartli masalalarni yechishni Galyorkin usulidan foydalanamiz. Hamda uning qiymatini hisoblash uchun Python dasturlash tilidagi algoritmdan foydalangan holda hisoblashni yoritib berganmiz. Yechim α ning turli qiymatlari uchun chizilgan.

Kalit soʻzlar: Kaputo kasr tartibli hosila va integral, Galyorkin metodi

Annotation: In this article, we use the Galerkin to solve the initial and bordering issues for fractional differential equations. And we covered the calculation of the Python programming algorithm to calculate its value. The solution is drawn for different values of α .

Keywords: Caputo fractional derivative and fractional integral, Galerkin method

Hozirgi vaqtda kasr tartibli integral va hosilalar nazariyasi funksiyalar nazariyasining tarmoqlaridan biri boʻlib, muhim amaliy ahamiyatga ega boʻlmoqda [1-6]. Kasr tartibli hosila va integrallarga asoslangan matematik modellar matematik biologiyada [7], gidrogeologiyada issiqlik va massa almashinish jarayonlarini bir xil boʻlmagan muhitda modellashda [8-10], transonik oqimlarning elastoplastiklik muammolari, yarimoʻtkazgichlar sohasidagi tadqiqotlar, epidemiologiyada, moliya va boshqa yoʻnalishlarda eʼtirof etiladi.

Kasr tartibli integrallar va hosilalar oʻziga xos xususiyatlarga ega va kasr integrallari va hosilalari bilan tenglamalarni echishning analitik usullari har doim ham samarali emas. Soʻnggi yillarda sonli usullar keng rivojlandi. Biroq, ushbu yoʻnalishda erishilgan muvaffaqiyatlarga qaramay, shunga oʻxshash muammolarning umumiy sinfi uchun taqribiy usullardan foydalanishni nazariy asoslash masalasi ochiqlicha qolmoqda.

Aytaylik $\alpha > 0$ va $n = \alpha$ bo'lsin. Kaputo α kasr tartibli hosila quyidagicha ta'riflanadi:

$${}^C D_t^\alpha f(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(n-\alpha)} \int_a^t (t-u)^{n-\alpha-1} \left(\frac{d}{du}\right)^n f(u) du$$

$a=0$ uchun, quyidagicha belgilash kiritamiz:

$${}^C D_t^\alpha f(t) = D^\alpha f(t).$$

Endi esa quyidagi chegaraviy shartlar bilan masala uchun Galyo'rkin metodini ko'rib chiqaylik.

$$\begin{aligned} D^\alpha y(t) + f(t) &= 0, \\ y(0) &= 0, \quad y(1) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

bu yerda $0 < t < 1$, $0 < \alpha \leq 1$ va $f(t)$ berilgan funksiya.

$R(t)$ orqali tenglamaning qoldiq hadini belgilaymiz va u quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$R(t) = D^\alpha y_a(t) + f(t),$$

bu yerda $y_a(t)$ $y(t)$ ning taqribiy yani aproksimatsiya qilingan qiymat bo'lib uni quyidagi ko'rinishda izlaymiz:

$$y_a(t) = \sum_{i=1}^N C_i \phi_i(t)$$

bu yerda $\phi_i(t)$ og'rilik funksiyalari, shuningdek:

$$\int_0^1 R(t) \phi_i(t) (dt)^\alpha = 0, \quad i=1,2,\dots,N,$$

$$\int_0^1 \left[D^\alpha y_a(t) + f(t) \right] \phi_i(t) (dt)^\alpha = 0, \quad i=1,2,\dots,N,$$

$$\int_0^1 D^\alpha y_a(t) \phi_i(t) (dt)^\alpha = - \int_0^1 f(t) \phi_i(t) (dt)^\alpha, \quad i=1,2,\dots,N.$$

1-misol. Quyidagi shartlar bilan berilgan kasr tartibli differensial tenglama taqribiy yechimini topish uchun Galo‘rkin metodidan foydalaning.

$$D^\alpha y(t) - t = 0,$$

$$y(0) = 0, y^{(\alpha)}(0) = 0, 0 < \alpha \leq 1.$$

Yechish. Og‘irlik funksiyasini quyidagicha tanlaymiz:

$$\phi_1 = t, \phi_2 = t^2,$$

va yechim quyidagi ko‘rinishga keladi:

$$y_a = C_1 t + C_2 t^2.$$

Quyidagiga ega bo‘lamiz:

$$D^\alpha y_a = C_1 D^\alpha t + C_2 D^\alpha t^2.$$

natijada formulalar:

$$D^\alpha t^k = \frac{\Gamma(k+1)}{\Gamma(k+1-\alpha)} t^{k-\alpha},$$

$$I^\alpha t^k = \frac{\Gamma(k+1)}{\Gamma(k+1+\alpha)} t^{k+\alpha},$$

$$D^\alpha y_a = C_1 \frac{\Gamma(1+1)}{\Gamma(1+1-\alpha)} t^{1-\alpha} + C_2 \frac{\Gamma(2+1)}{\Gamma(2+1-\alpha)} t^{2-\alpha},$$

Vanihyot, quyidagi sistemaga kelamiz:

$$\begin{cases} \int \left[C_1 \frac{2}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} t^{1-\alpha} + C_2 \frac{2}{\Gamma(3-\alpha)} t^{2-\alpha} \right] t (dt)^\alpha = \int_0^1 t^2 (dt)^\alpha \\ \int \left[C_1 \frac{2}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} t^{1-\alpha} + C_2 \frac{2}{\Gamma(3-\alpha)} t^{2-\alpha} \right] t^2 (dt)^\alpha = \int_0^1 t^3 (dt)^\alpha \end{cases}$$

yoki:

$$\begin{cases} C_1 \frac{2}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} \frac{\Gamma(3-\alpha)}{\Gamma(3)} + C_2 \frac{2}{\Gamma(3-\alpha)} \frac{\Gamma(4-\alpha)}{\Gamma(4)} = \frac{\Gamma(3)}{\Gamma(3+\alpha)} \\ C_1 \frac{2}{\Gamma(2-\alpha)} \frac{\Gamma(4-\alpha)}{\Gamma(4)} + C_2 \frac{2}{\Gamma(3-\alpha)} \frac{\Gamma(5-\alpha)}{\Gamma(5)} = \frac{\Gamma(4)}{\Gamma(4+\alpha)} \end{cases}$$

Yuqoridagi sistemani Python dasturlash tilida tuzilgan quydagi dastur orqali aniqlaymiz.

```
import numpy as np
from scipy.special import gamma, factorial
```



```
a=0.5
B11=2/gamma(2-a)*gamma(3-a)/gamma(3)
B12=2/gamma(3-a)*gamma(4-a)/gamma(4)
B21=2/gamma(2-a)*gamma(4-a)/gamma(4)
B22=2/gamma(3-a)*gamma(5-a)/gamma(5)
F1=gamma(3)/gamma(3+a)
F2=gamma(4)/gamma(4 + a)
b=np.array([[B11,B12],[B21,B22]])
f=np.array([F1,F2])
c=np.linalg.solve(b, f)
c
```

$\alpha = 0.50$ uchun $C_1 = 0.17194349$, $C_2 = 0.41266438$, $\alpha = 1$ uchun $C_1 = 0$, $C_2 = 0.5$.

2-misol. Quyidagi chegaraviy shartlar bilan berilgan kasr tartibli differensial tenglama uchun taqribiy yechimni Gelo‘rkin metodidan foydalanib quring:

$$D^{2\alpha} y(t) + t = 0,$$
$$y(0) = 0, y(1) = 0, 0 < \alpha \leq 1.$$

Yechim. Og‘irlik funksiyasini quyidagicha tanlaymiz:

$$v_1 = t^2(1-t), v_2 = t^2(1-t^2),$$

va taqribiy yechim:

$$y_a = C_1 v_1 + C_2 v_2.$$

Quyidagilarga egamiz:

$$D^{2\alpha} y_a = C_1 D^{2\alpha} v_1 + C_2 D^{2\alpha} v_2,$$

$$D^{2\alpha} t^k = \frac{\Gamma(k+1)}{\Gamma(k+1-2\alpha)} t^{k-2\alpha},$$

va Galerkin sistemasi:

$$\begin{cases} \int_0^1 D^{2\alpha} y_a v_1 (dt)^\alpha = 0 \\ \int_0^1 D^{2\alpha} y_a v_2 (dt)^\alpha = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$\begin{cases} C_1 \int_0^1 D^{2\alpha} v_1 v_1 (dt)^\alpha + C_2 \int_0^1 D^{2\alpha} v_2 v_1 (dt)^\alpha = - \int_0^1 t v_1 (dt)^\alpha \\ C_1 \int_0^1 D^{2\alpha} v_1 v_2 (dt)^\alpha + C_2 \int_0^1 D^{2\alpha} v_2 v_2 (dt)^\alpha = - \int_0^1 t v_2 (dt)^\alpha \end{cases}$$

Quyidagicha belgilashlar kiritamiz:

$$A = \frac{2}{\Gamma(3-2\alpha)}, \quad B = \frac{6}{\Gamma(4-2\alpha)}, \quad C = \frac{24}{\Gamma(2-2\alpha)},$$

va bundan quyidagilar kelib chiqadi:

$$D^{2\alpha} v_1 = D^{2\alpha} t^2 (1-t) = At^{2-2\alpha} - Bt^{3-2\alpha},$$

$$D^{2\alpha} v_2 = D^{2\alpha} (t^2 - t^4) = At^{2-2\alpha} - Ct^{4-2\alpha},$$

$$(D^{2\alpha} v_1) v_1 = At^{4-2\alpha} - Bt^{5-2\alpha} - At^{5-2\alpha} + Bt^{6-2\alpha},$$

$$(D^{2\alpha} v_1) v_2 = At^{4-2\alpha} - Bt^{5-2\alpha} - At^{6-2\alpha} + Bt^{7-2\alpha},$$

$$(D^{2\alpha} v_2) v_1 = At^{4-2\alpha} - At^{5-2\alpha} - Ct^{6-2\alpha} + Ct^{7-2\alpha},$$

$$(D^{2\alpha} v_2) v_2 = At^{4-2\alpha} - At^{6-2\alpha} - Ct^{6-2\alpha} + Ct^{8-2\alpha},$$

$$B_{11} = \int_0^1 (D^{2\alpha} v_1) v_1 (dt)^\alpha = A \frac{\Gamma(5-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(5-\alpha)} - B \frac{\Gamma(6-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(6-\alpha)} - A \frac{\Gamma(6-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(6-\alpha)} + B \frac{\Gamma(7-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(7-\alpha)}$$

$$B_{12} = \int_0^1 (D^{2\alpha} v_1) v_2 (dt)^\alpha = A \frac{\Gamma(5-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(5-\alpha)} - B \frac{\Gamma(6-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(6-\alpha)} - A \frac{\Gamma(7-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(7-\alpha)} + B \frac{\Gamma(8-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(8-\alpha)}$$

$$B_{21} = \int_0^1 (D^{2\alpha} v_2) v_1 (dt)^\alpha = A \frac{\Gamma(5-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(5-\alpha)} - A \frac{\Gamma(6-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(6-\alpha)} - C \frac{\Gamma(7-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(7-\alpha)} + C \frac{\Gamma(8-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(8-\alpha)}$$

$$B_{22} = \int_0^1 (D^{2\alpha} v_2) v_2 (dt)^\alpha = A \frac{\Gamma(5-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(5-\alpha)} - A \frac{\Gamma(7-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(7-\alpha)} - C \frac{\Gamma(7-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(7-\alpha)} + C \frac{\Gamma(9-2\alpha)}{\Gamma(9-\alpha)}$$

$$F_1 = - \int_0^1 t v_1 (dt)^\alpha = - \frac{\Gamma(4)}{\Gamma(4+\alpha)} + \frac{\Gamma(5)}{\Gamma(5+\alpha)},$$

$$F_2 = -\int_0^1 tv_2(dt)^\alpha = -\frac{\Gamma(4)}{\Gamma(4+\alpha)} + \frac{\Gamma(6)}{\Gamma(6+\alpha)}.$$

Quyidagi belgilashdan foydalanib,

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} B_{11} & B_{12} \\ B_{21} & B_{22} \end{pmatrix},$$

$$C = [C_1 \ C_2],$$

$$F = [F_1 \ F_2],$$

quyidagilarga ega bo‘lamiz:

$$BC^T = F^T \Rightarrow C^T = B^{-1}F^T.$$

Yuqorida aniqlanganlar ga ko‘raPython dasturlash tilida quyidagi dasturidan foydalanib C_1 va C_2 larni hisoblaymiz

```
import numpy as np
from scipy.special import gamma, factorial
a=0.5
A=2/gamma(3-2*a)
B=6/gamma(4-2*a)
C=24/gamma(5-2*a)
B11=A*gamma(5-2*a)/gamma(5-a)-B * gamma(6 - 2 * a)/gamma(6 - a)- A *
gamma(6 - 2 * a)/gamma(6 - a)+ B * gamma(7 - 2 * a)/gamma(7 - a)
B12=A * gamma(5 - 2 * a)/gamma(5 - a) - B * gamma(6 - 2 * a)/gamma(6 - a) -
A * gamma(7 - 2 * a)/gamma(7 - a)+ B * gamma(8 - 2 * a)/gamma(8 - a)
B21=A * gamma(5 - 2 * a)/gamma(5 - a) - A * gamma(6 - 2 * a)/gamma(6 - a) -
C * gamma(7 - 2 * a)/gamma(7 - a)+ C * gamma(8 - 2 * a)/gamma(8 - a)
B22=A * gamma(5 - 2 * a)/gamma(5 - a) - A * gamma(7 - 2 * a)/gamma(7 - a)-
C * gamma(7 - 2 * a)/gamma(7 - a) + C * gamma(9 - 2 * a)/gamma(9 - a)
F1=-gamma(4)/gamma(4 + a)+ gamma(5)/gamma(5 + a)
F2=-gamma(4)/gamma(4 + a)+ gamma(6)/gamma(6 + a)
b=np.array([[B11,B12],[B21,B22]])
f=np.array([F1,F2])
c=np.linalg.solve(b, f)
c
a = 0.5 uchun C1 = -16.25, C2 = 9.75
a = 1 uchun C1 = 1.05555556, C2 = -0.38888889
```

Yuqoridagi kabi masalalar [6-10] ishlarda ham ko‘rilgan/

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro‘yxati

1. Самко С.Г., Килбасс А.А, Маричев О.И. Интегралы и производные дробного порядка и некоторые их приложения. Минск, 1987.
2. Нахушев А.М. Элементы дробного исчисления и их применение. Нальчик, 2000.
3. А.К.Уринов, С.М.Ситник, Э.Л.Шишкина, Ш.Т.Каримов. Дробные интегралы и производные (обобщения и приложения): учебное пособие; учебно-методическое издание; на русском языке; А.Уринов и др. Фергана: изд. “Фаргона”, 2022.-192 стр.
4. Уринов А.К., Каримов Ш.Т. Операторы Эрдейи-Кобера и их приложения к дифференциальным уравнениям в частных производных: монография; научное издание; на русском языке; /А.К.Уринов, Ш.Т. Каримов. Фергана: изд. “Фаргона”, 2021. -202 стр.
5. Fractional Calculus and its Applications, lecture notes in mathematics/ Ed. Ross B. Berlin, 1975.
6. Каримов Ш.Т. О некоторых обобщениях свойств оператора Эрдейи-Кобера и их приложение. Вестник КРАУНЦ. Физ.-мат. науки. 2017. № 2(18). С. 20-40. DOI: 10.18454/2079-6641-2017-18-2-20-40.
7. Каримов Ш.Т. Новые свойства обобщенного оператора Эрдейи – Кобера и их приложения. Доклады АН РУз. – 2014. -№ 5 -С. 11-13.
8. Karimov Sh. T. New Properties of Generalized Erdélyi–Kober Operator With Application. Dokl. Akad. Nauk Uzbek Republic. . – 2014. -№ 5 -С. 11-13.
9. Karimov Sh. T. About some generalizations of the properties of the Erdelyi–Kober operator and their application. Vestnik KRAUNC. Fiziko-Matematicheskie Nauki. 2017. № 2. С. 20-40.
10. Каримов Ш.Т., Хайдарова С. Численное решение периодических уравнений с дробно-интегральным оператором Вейля в главной части. Fars Int J Edu Soc Sci Hum 10(12), 2022; Volume-10, Issue-12, pp. 152-157.

